

Staff Exchange Schemes (x2)

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1. Introduction

The workplan for this project is located within Work Package 5 which focuses on planning and development of short-term (2 years) activities under Network and Strategic Initiatives department. Its aim is to deepen understanding and awareness between national entrepreneurship ecosystem governance bodies and ESNA.

For this purpose, a specific staff-exchange scheme has been created, allowing interchange between officers and experts of different ecosystems and ESNA.

Staff exchange has been established to support all 4 Action Areas within ESNA:

1. **Standards and Policy:** interchange knowledge and factual information regarding each country's national policies within the startup ecosystem by observing Startup Nation Standards score.
2. **Insights and Analytics:** extend knowledge and data points to be included within digital Data Hub.
3. **Network and Strategic Initiatives:** develop and strengthen links between national policy makers and ESNA.
4. **Marketing and Communications:** strengthen ESNA's position as the common voice and communication channel for national startup ecosystems in Europe.

The program is established with two clear objectives in mind:

1. **Strengthen Relationships:** Develop actions to strengthen relationships and enhance awareness among national ecosystem players in Europe
2. **Knowledge Sharing:** Create a space to share knowledge between ESNA and its members.

2. Program Design and Structure

The staff exchange program was initially planned exclusively between ESNA and its member entities. During the program set-up it became evident that while there is on-going and consistent information exchange between ESNA's members, there is a need and also active interest to build knowledge sharing with a higher political mandate represented by each country. Considering these aspects, additional objectives have been identified for this particular work package:

- Establish a higher political relationship between ESNA and its signatory countries that are yet to nominate a formal entity to represent their interests within ESNA.
- Strengthen existing relationships between ESNA and its members by conducting in-depth reviews of ESNA's activities and engage in future plans.

The staff exchange program operates within the framework of requests for scheduled meetings between ESNA and its signatory countries' representatives. These meetings serve as the platform for the exchange, facilitating dialogue, collaboration, and knowledge transfer between representatives from ESNA and participating countries.

The duration and intensity of each staff exchange session depends on the attendees and the subjects under discussion. While the specific length of the meetings may vary, the exchange is an ongoing endeavour that will extend over the course of ESNA's operations.

3. Program's Timeline

The staff exchange program under Work Package 5 of the Network and Strategic Initiatives department has progressed through a series of engagements aimed at fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing between ESNA and its signatory countries. The timeline below outlines key milestones and meetings conducted thus far:

Pilot meetings served as guidelines for scoping the initiative further:

1. Belgium Exchange

- Meeting Date: 20th September 2023
- Planning and preparation initiated on 29th of August by ESNA's Board of Director's initiative.
- Purpose of the meeting: provide an update on ESNA's activities and give guidance for preparation for Belgium to be part of ESNA's Presidency Board starting 2024.

2. Luxembourg Exchange

- Meeting Date: 13th November 2023
- Planning and preparation initiated on 15th September upon request from Luxembourg.
- Purpose of the meeting: Luxembourg formally joined ESNA earlier the same year (June 2023) and this was one of the first higher level political meeting and exchange concerning ESNA's existing and future activities.

Following the two pilot exchanges conducted, the program was officially initiated in January 2024 with the following meetings held to date:

1. France Exchange

- Meeting Date: 12th January 2024
- Planning and preparation initiated on 18th December upon request from France's member entity
- Purpose of the meeting: France embassy in Portugal expressed interest in learning more about ESNA and engage in a conversation about the future action plan. This contact was facilitated by ESNA's member representing France, who connected the respective Embassy contact directly with ESNA.

2. Portugal Exchange:

- Meeting Date: 18th March 2024
- Planning and preparation initiated on 14th of March upon request from ESNA
- Purpose of the meeting: One of key projects led by ESNA is the Data Hub that will bring together startup ecosystem relevant high-level data. This exchange was held to learn from ESNA's Portuguese member of their experience and learnings with similar projects. ESNA was guided through the process of the member's Data Platform procedure, highlighting important challenges and aspects to be considered within ESNA's procedure.

3. Netherlands Exchange

- Meeting Date: 14th of May 2024
- Planning and preparation initiated on the 22nd of April upon request from the Netherlands
- Purpose of the meeting: Embassy of the Netherlands has expressed interest in learning more about ESNA and its activities. As Netherlands has not yet formally nominated a member to join ESNA, this meeting required a more in-depth discussion of ESNA's existing and planned activities

4. Spain Exchange:

- Meeting Date: 5th of June 2024
- Planning and preparation initiated on the 27th of May upon request from ESNA team
- Purpose of the meeting: share ESNA's most recent activities and status of current action plan with a focus on new initiative launched in April (Service Line) and learn ESNA's members current needs and areas of support.

The exchange sessions are initiated based on requests and expressed interest from the signatory country representatives or by ESNA inviting the entity or country representatives for such exchange. Each meeting serves as an opportunity for ESNA and the respective country representatives to engage in discussions, share insights, and explore areas of mutual interest.

The agenda for each exchange typically includes an overview of ESNA and its current and future activities. Additionally, there are discussions on specific projects or initiatives of interest to the national representatives, with ESNA providing insights and answering questions. Equally, ESNA may also inquire about particular areas of interest for the national representatives, fostering a mutual exchange of information and ideas.

Outcomes and potential areas for future collaboration are evaluated through subsequent interactions and additional requests from participating countries.

4. Evaluation of the Program and Next Steps

The evaluation of the staff exchange program reflects its high political significance and the fluid nature of engagements between ESNA and its signatory countries. The success of the program is assessed indirectly through subsequent exchanges and collaborative actions. Key aspects of the evaluation include:

- **Establishment of Higher Political Relationships:** The program aims to establish higher political relationships between ESNA and signatory countries that have yet to nominate a formal entity to represent their interests within ESNA. The effectiveness of this objective is assessed through ongoing engagements and the occurrence of collaborative opportunities.
- **Strengthening Existing Relationships:** An in-depth review of ESNA activities and engagement on future plans is conducted during the exchange sessions to strengthen relationships between ESNA and its member entities. Success in this regard is measured by the depth of engagement and the continuity of collaborative efforts.

Building on the achievements and lessons learned from the staff exchange program, the following next steps are proposed:

- **Continued Support for Member Requests:** ESNA will continue to support requests for staff exchange and knowledge-sharing initiatives from its member entities. This includes actively facilitating engagements and providing necessary resources to ensure the success of such actions.
- **Proactive Pursuit of Opportunities:** In addition to responding to member requests, ESNA will proactively seek out opportunities for staff exchange and collaboration with signatory countries. By actively engaging with stakeholders and fostering dialogue, ESNA aims to expand its network and deepen its impact within the European startup ecosystem.

In addition, ESNA has ensured availability of a physical meeting space to offer its members a location to host and be welcomed for further exchanges in Lisbon. These steps are aligned with ESNA's overarching mission to promote collaboration, innovation, and growth within the European startup ecosystem, and will serve as a roadmap for future activities.

5. Conclusions

Staff Exchange program under Work Package 5 has been instrumental in fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing between ESNA and its signatory countries. The importance of a higher political interaction between ESNA and its signatory countries have been confirmed through the series of engagements. Such initiative is crucial to strengthen the relationship and ensure advancement of mutual understanding of startup ecosystem in each country.

The program has highlighted the need to broaden the “recipients” of the program to initiate and strengthen the dialogue at a higher political level between ESNA and its members. Moreover, the program has underscored the importance of proactive engagement and knowledge sharing in advancing the collective goals of ESNA and its member entities.

It is evident that exchange initiatives play a crucial role in building bridges, fostering understanding, and driving collective action. The program serves to increase power of collaboration and the transformative impact of shared knowledge and experiences. Moving forward, ESNA remains committed to leveraging such initiatives to drive positive change and unlock new opportunities for innovation and growth to collectively shape European startup ecosystem.

6. Appendix

Due to the nature of this document (Public) names of participants of each meeting including other sensitive documents are available upon request to ESNA. Those documents include:

- Participants of each meeting
- Documents supporting preparation (email exchanges)
- Documents supporting the meeting itself (presentations)